

The Analysis & Proposed Implementation of Blockchain technology in Record Security Management in the Bank Industry of Zambia

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Abstract: Bank record security management is vital to the financial security of every nation. It aims to safeguard residents' as well as government income, determines eligibility for social assistance, and has a substantial influence on a country's foreign relations, economy and reputation. Numerous efforts are now ongoing throughout the globe to increase and improve security in the financial industry, especially in developing nations where demand is highest. It is common knowledge that the qualities of blockchain technology promote efficiency, transparency, and confidence. Concerns over data security, the danger of cybercrime, and the efficacy of bank system security are growing, especially in nations like Zambia that are still developing. Even after years later, it seems the banks and Ministry of Finance are unable to verify and assure the country's money is 100% secure, even inside the banks, according to information acquired and based on several interviews about bank security, the existence of a firewall is where all faith lies. Even after registration, there is no guarantee that client information is entirely secure and inaccessible to unauthorized third parties. This raises concerns and dangers about deceit being possible. In Zambia's bank record security management, there have been instances of illegal data changes and more recently, a cybercrime-related data breach. Throughout the years, government and public monies have been misappropriated without any documents to indicate what transpired or what happened to the revenue, and who knows what else.

If the institution's information system is made safer and more dependable, process verification problems may be resolved. This research has been engaged with the aim of developing model design that employs blockchain technology principles to enhance Zambia's Record Security Management in banks. The later section of this research has an inclusion of a summary of the various literature about blockchain technology and Bank Record Security Management that is relevant. It describes the standard registry, storage, and operations, as well as a general description of blockchain, including its characteristics and uses.

It demonstrates that using blockchain technology might boost efficiency by decreasing human labour and paper processing, and by giving clear provenance that verifies the origin of products. It may be used in industries such as health, education, agriculture, real estate, Bank record Security Management, etc. It also proves that smart contracts have a vast future potential, and that Ethereum is one of the most suitable platforms for constructing distributed applications using smart contracts. To fulfil the objective of the research, it was important to investigate Zambia's Record Security Management procedures in order to uncover continuing problems related with unauthorized alterations and other reported concerns. The Bank Blockchain Adoption Framework guided the examination of process mapping, stages and data. The results allow us to break Bank RSM into three phases: registration, verification and lastly, storage.

Using a flowchart process diagram, network architecture, use cases, and technological development diagrams, a full design solution is shown. This project in design science offers a blockchain-based application architecture that will enhance the existing Bank Record Security Management System. It is proposed that the blockchain network be used to share datasets between banks, other financial organizations, and other informatics under the Ministry of Home Affairs Security. On the other hand, a centralized server will be an operating node in the blockchain network that is where records will be stored digitally. The research built a novel registration method on the Ethereum blockchain on Binance Smart Chain using the React App client, which in this case is the NodeJS server's web interface. The architecture was used to assess a smart contract's verification implementation. The NodeJS Server uses the web3 library plugin to interface with the Ethereum client network. Bank Record Security Management based on blockchain technology may enhance the security and integrity of banks and nations.

This study's contribution may be utilized for additional research in each of the aforementioned application areas to uncover potential benefits and drawbacks.

Keywords: Bank Record Security Management, blockchain technology, Ethereum Network, Zambia research

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1. Introduction

We are living times in which technology is at its peak & the internet is the main resource for every piece of information. Research is ongoing as more & more discoveries are being made in the world wide web thus resulting in further & continuous research. Recently researchers' eyes have been caught by the spawn & ongoing growth of Blockchain Technology (BCT) not just as an application of Cryptocurrency but as a tool in solving social challenges with the use of centralized databases. [1], states that the Technology known as Blockchain has the great potential to substitute central banking systems as well as other use cases like as business process optimization, trading, medical information exchange, automobile possession & polling. [2] says, Blockchain technology is a method for producing and storing trustworthy digital records. This article discusses some of the approach's limits, concerns, and prospects. According to [3], BCT can also put an end to the ongoing cybercrimes.

Nevertheless, as blockchain technology advances proliferate, there is growing worry about information security and the efficacy of record processing as well as storage in various institutions such as banks. Currently, open banking is confronted with several problems significant challenges, including variations in data management practices used by various banks, financial organizations, and other consumers [4]. Misappropriation and theft, bribery and kickbacks, money laundering, other unlawful capital flow, and state control are major hurdles to achieving and maintaining prosperity in Africa. [5]. In many developing & second-world and third-world countries, national revenue has sprung forth visible results which ease the minds of citizens as they know their taxes & national revenue are being used correctly & for various things such as creation of more opportunities as well as paving way for further national development. But nowadays citizens are left baffled & continue inquiring about the national revenue as they do not know why nations are getting into more dept despite increase in the availability of investors, manufacturing institutions & more. Zambia's increasing adaptation to mobile banking & the growth of the world wide web has raised concerns of cybercrime. Already there have been a few cases that occurred. In their review, [6] mentioned that conversations about cyber security

and a bank's security architecture should be a top priority. In 2021, [7], brought back the same issue stating that as the banking industry continues to extend its digital presence and the variety of ways it interacts with clients grows, so does the danger of cyber-attacks. The continuous integration of banks, mobile network services, and network operators has caused an increase in the number of potential sources of vulnerability. Stated in their report, [8] stated that there are rising concerns & doubts about the payment's security such as risk control, and data protection are all important elements in a customer's choice to convert from traditional to digital forms of payment. State capture is one major issue that has been in existence in Zambia as well as in Africa. State capture happens when the governing class &/or influential corporate individuals manage policy development and influence the evolving rules of the game (such as laws, customs, and economic regulations) to benefit themselves rather than the public good [5]. For decades financial institutions such as banks in Zambia have been pawns in this.

According to [9] Making sure that records or stored data is reliable is a necessity in a various situations and sectors in which different record systems offer key fundamental facilities required in making sure development goals are met. [10] suggest that central banks also could look into the placing of software that watches e-banks records the actions of all banks and other financial organisations in real time. Therefore, it will confine them then force them to perform professionally. Various researchers have suggested blockchain technology as the most recommended way to adhere protection of data. In case of scenarios like that which is happening in Zambia, application of BCT known as the Distributed Ledger would be the best application used to protect, authenticate as well as monitor Bank Transaction Records. In their report, [11] stated that the usage of distributed ledgers is particularly useful & advantageous to the country's strong devotion to personal information privacy & its excellent reputation for rule of law a rising group of literature has clarified concerning immense advantages that technology like that of Distributed Ledgers, for example, blockchain, contribute to technical advancements. According to [12], Blockchain technology gives us a bright future free of deceit and fraud. Blockchain technology may have a significant influence on future business models, as evidenced by the example of banks in all sectors [13]. It is, nevertheless, insufficient for implementation and use in a range of scenarios. Many limitations will spring forth. Thus, the application will need broader looking into. Based on various research as well as analysis it has been discovered that blockchain is new and not many organisations, countries and Financial institutions have given it the attention it deserves especially looking at its uses and application when we talk of addressing concerns centred around bank record security management. Nonetheless, much of the research has been limited to economy powerhouses such as China and the United States of America, with little attention paid to its application in the context of certain second-world, even worse, third-world, countries such as Zambia. This underlines the necessity to study and adopt a solution based on blockchain technology to solve the Republic of Zambia's current Bank Record Security Management issue.

The project has a primary objective is to create a model designed to use and run Blockchain Chain Technology theories to enhance procedures in Bank Record Security Management in a commercial bank in Zambia. This study specifically seeks to accomplish the following goals:

- To offer a comprehensive summary of the present situation of the Banking Record Security Management System infrastructure in Zambia.
- Detection of current system weaknesses and inefficiencies.
- Determination & investigation of blockchain Technology as a feasible tool for filling current inefficiencies.
- To investigate not just the potential benefits of a solution that is based on blockchain technology but also the practicality of using this technology.

To propose & test a new solution based on blockchain Technology.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Background

2.1.1 Back Record Security Management governance

Records are main sources of documentation gathered over the course of an organization's lifespan that demonstrate that organization's actions. Archives store documents that have been chosen by the organization for permanent or long-term preservation due to their historical, vital, or evidential importance, documentation that will allow the bank to re-establish its activities and institutions. In the case of absolute calamity, the institution's legal and financial standing will be preserved, as will the rights of its workers and stockholders. Records offer proof of decisions and actions done in the course of carrying out or supporting the Bank's operations. They record and preserve the Bank Group's policies, decisions, contracts, procedures, operations, and transactions. They must be kept until their administrative, legal, or budgetary purpose expires. Beyond the legislative requirements, the authorized authority, in collaboration with the Secretary General, may establish that certain documents have important historical and cultural significance. These documents must be retained in perpetuity [14]. Most banking apps have failed to withstand the continuously increasing assaults on their customers' sensitive data. Ongoing fraud issues working in a typical context. However, present solutions are still attempting to deal with the existing institutional framework, which is truly designed for traditional banking systems and not for better managing their customers' information. The lack of proper security measures makes it very difficult to effectively shift bank customers' management systems from where they are today to where they should be. This difficulty is still present. These days, financial institutions are looking more than just transactions to the entire potential of how to manage their customers. As a consequence of this, they are shifting from managing clients as basic contacts to an entirely new level of client relationship management. As a result of this, they are designing a better commercial client experience, which gives the bank an advantage over its competitors and results in more customers who are loyal, profitable, and committed. Internet Banking Systems are systems that enable customers of financial institutions to have access to their bank accounts as well as general information on the products and services offered by the institution through a personal computer or other intelligent device. On the other hand, the bulk of these solutions do not focus on how to better manage and protect the data of their consumers. There is no longer any surprise in the fact that the internet brings both possibilities and problems to the contemporary banking industry. Without an online strategy, no conventional bank would dare to confront investment analysts or new clients. The primary goal of launching electronic banking services is to give clients with a more responsive and cost-effective alternative. Customers have more power than they ever had before because to the increased level of security offered by solutions. Their expectations centre on the confidentiality and protection of the information that identifies them personally. Additionally, they need individualized attention in addition to highly customized products and services.. [15].

Resistance to fraud may be obtained by analysing a massive amount of data to generate fraud-proof client profiles. However, openness allows crooks to modify profiles to their advantage. Blind automation is a potential threat [16]. Payment system providers are expected to improve their cyber security resilience in order to respond to upcoming changes in the risk environment and new types of technology advances under Vision 2022. Furthermore, given the numerous interconnections and interdependencies of payment systems, sufficient cyber security measures must be implemented across the National Payment System. It is vital to improve the overall cyber security resilience of payment systems. The total National Payment System's cyber security resilience is based not just on the resilience of a single payment system, but also on the resilience of linked payment systems [17]. They propose establishing a national cyber security monitoring system and developing a method for reporting crimes to authorities. The framework should enable information exchange among service providers and regulators, as well as the adoption of international standards on cyber security and resilience, as well as regular inspections and testing of payment system cyber resilience. To

accomplish this, the Customer/Originator must keep up-to-date records and processes in place to ensure that payments are made accurately and on time [18].

Opportunities may be hampered by government budgets and corruption. Concerns about fiscal shortfalls have hurt the confidence of the Republic of Zambia's ratings of credit and investor. Corruption index ratings continue to be high, and new research reveal that public image of corruption is improving. This has a direct negative impact on company confidence. In contrast, the recent downgrading by avoiding correspondent banking agreements, payment companies may reduce their dependency on USD [19]. Zambia is not a large hub of finances. Majority of money that is laundered comes from illegal activities such as drug dealing, bribery, and corruption in public office. Problems may also arise from human trafficking, the trade in endangered species, and the wood industry. The institutions that are used most often in the process of money laundering which includes banks, real estate sector brokers, insurance companies, and legal companies and more. In order to conceal their ill-gotten gains, criminals in Zambia have resorted to money laundering techniques such as structuring, currency swaps, monetary instruments, gaming, undervaluing commodities, asset misappropriation, and front businesses are all examples of fraudulent business practices. The use of securities, debit and credit cards, smuggling large amounts of cash, wire transfers, fake currency certifications, and other practices and trade based money laundering (TBML), which involves in addition to the abusive trade mis-invoicing of regular trade items, the acquisition of luxury items such as vehicles and real estate. It is not common practice to consider Zambia to be a significant offshore financial centre. The government of the Republic of Zambia is now in the process of constructing a variety of economic zones that are equipped with many facilities., which are intended to function in a manner similar to free trading areas [20].

Low human and institutional capability, a paucity of investigators and prosecutors, and inefficient oversight, notably of the banking sector, are among the primary difficulties confronting Zambia's AML (Anti Money Laundering) system. The prevalence of corruption, as well as the dominance of cash transactions, exacerbate the problem [21].

According to [7], there might be significant the price of upgrading certain vital information infrastructure and systems to satisfy security responsibilities, such as the officials continue to monitor traffic. Our There are some who have invested, according to experience. in cybersecurity, and those that trail far behind.

- Overall regulatory compliance - Market players will be held accountable. Obligated to comply with the Act's provisions, and would need the development of policies aiming at putting in appropriate measures.
- Employee awareness and training - Financial institutions will need this. help plan industry-specific awareness campaigns and Ensure that all employees are aware of the Act's ramifications.
- Data security concerns - Data security problems will surely result from the Act's implementation. Organizations must be aware of the difficulties that may arise. up in their day-to-day operations and disclosures that must be provided to consumers.

2.1.2 Blockchain Technology

A blockchain is a kind of distributed ledger that is made up of a chain of cryptographically interconnected 'blocks' that include batching transactions; it typically distributes all data to all network members [22]. Blockchain is similar to a database in that it arranges records into blocks in a ledger rather than keeping them in tables. Each new block is tied like a chain to a preceding block using a cryptographic hash, thus the term Blockchain. The ledger may be shared with all members in the network and will undergo verification and also validation at the same time. In blockchain blocks are generated in something knowns as consensus mechanism. The consensus mechanism functions as a communal decision-making process in which each participant in a network contributes in order to identify the proper ledger version [23]. Consensus is the basic aspect of blockchain that dictates its architecture and is the key to creating trust among untrustworthy parties [24]. Reliability of records is necessary in a number of situations where systems of record provide the key infrastructure required to accomplish development objectives. This comprises banks

and other financial institutions such as credit unions, savings and loans groups, and insurance companies, investment companies, brokerage firms, insurance companies, mortgage companies and more. [25] says that blockchain is altering the digital world by offering a fresh viewpoint to system security, resilience, and efficiency. In their account, [26] lay out the some benefits of Blockchain Technology in financial institutions as follows;

- Blockchain creates Cultural benefits, there is an increase in level of trust.
- It also provides regulatory benefits by reducing fraud and fraudulent transactions, improving compliance requirements, and enhancing auditability.
- Blockchain also contributes to Governance in that it maintains unchanging business norms, increased tractability and data record immutability.
- BCT can bring benefits in Market indicators as well such as Performance, in that processing and administrative cost will be reduced, not forgetting Reduced risk Increased efficiency.
- Blockchain can also cause an increase in infrastructure system resilience and provide a more Robust Automation.

Because of its attributes, blockchain technology could result in increases in efficiencies, accountability, and, as a result, trustworthiness. The following are some of the characteristics that define it:

a. Peer-to-peer Networking

The Peer-to-Peer Network system commonly known as Peer to Peer has no centralized host that exists in this, all available users are considered node holding capacity of the server. It provides techniques for cryptographic trust and assurance [27].

b. Cryptography

Cryptography is used in blockchain for authenticating, various forms of permission compliance, integrity verifying and many more purposes. Cryptography is the mathematical science of making communication secure [28]. Various approaches of cryptography are used, such as Cryptographic hash functions that are carried out in singular way, the Merkle trees, and also public key facilities, are used (private and also public keys pairs/doubles) [22].

c. Consensus Mechanism

[29] explains that central component of a Blockchain System describing how nodes does synchronization of the ledger is referred to as consensus mechanism. The consensus mechanism ensures that once a transaction is correctly recorded to the blockchain, the transaction record cannot be edited or compromised in the future [30].

d. Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)

Distributed Ledgers can increase the speed of transactions as well as lower associated costs by removing the need of a central authority [31]. Because the blockchain ledger is distributed, each node runs the same shared copy of the ledger, which gives it excellent resistance to breakdowns or malicious activity [27].

e. Timestamps

The timestamp shows when the block was made; the nonce is a random integer produced by the consensus process to calculate a block's hash code; the version represents the blockchain's version number; and the proof of difficulty is a generated hash value that must be met [32].

2.1.3 Smart Contracts

Smart Contracts according to [33] are defined as are self-executing contracts that include the details of an agreement among interested parties. They were proposed by Nick Szabo in 1997. A smart contract, according to Szabo's description, is a computerized transaction mechanism that performs the contract terms. The fundamental goal of a smart contract is

to meet the standard contractual requirements but automated by a fixed number of programmed lines of code [34]. They make blockchain more resistant to attacks [35]. To Points out some features of Smart contracts, these are:

1. Conditioned Nature - If the network node agrees on the conditions, smart contract processes are triggered [36].
2. Self-performance: Smart contracts are electronic contracts that the blockchain can execute automatically [37].
3. Self-sufficiency – They can also automatically conduct commercial transactions and agreements and enforce all parties' responsibilities without the additional cost of a middleman [38].

Smart contracts enable the transfer of value when certain criteria and conditions are satisfied. Contracts that exist in our world have same quite similar to these kinds of contracts. Mainly they are digitalized that's why they are totally different. The meaning of this is that their foundations are made up of some programming codes which are stored in systems called Distributed Ledgers. For instance, using Technology like Blockchain in financial trading to give assurance and backing to papers that are related to trade can reduce risk that come with loans and also the smart contracts, among many other things, can manage executing and launching of organisational activities between or among different organisations also publicly automate payments which are delayed or done in instalments. [39]. Also, Exporters, importers, and their banks may communicate information on a private distributed ledger using blockchain technology. The trade arrangement may then be automatically implemented using a series of digital smart contracts, which are written in computer code and can be performed automatically whenever certain conditions are met [40]. There is a need for regulatory governmental support in this application, as in many others that include a big group of stakeholders and span several areas and administrations. Furthermore, blockchain-based applications offer a hitherto untapped dimension in the form of capabilities that enable trust, traceability, and smart contracts. As a result, blockchain-based industrial applications demand increased degrees of government backing in a number of ways and capabilities (Al-Jaroodi & Mohamed, 2019). Although there are alternative platforms available, Ethereum is presently the most popular blockchain platform for writing smart contracts and is referred to as Blockchain 2.0 [42] [33]. Ethereum is the world's most commonly used and largest platform for constructing distributed applications, with applications ranging from social networks to identity systems, prediction markets, and a wide range of financial applications.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Approach

An exploratory technique is put to use when identifying the institution's present operation process in order to respond to the first research question. This required the usage of records and earlier studies outlining the present Bank Record Security Management methodology. The Bank Blockchain Adoption Framework, suggested by [43] as worldwide standards and best practices for bank record management, serves as the foundation for thematic content analysis. Based on the analysis done, a process outlining or modelling effort is carried out to characterize and assess the present processes, as shown in Table 1. Following that, issues in process outlining are discovered. Data obtained was to use and a strategy of implementation was created. The purpose of this was to fill in the gaps in the present facility or infrastructures and remove the problems connected with verifying. A blockchain architecture in future is recommended especially in places which maybe optimised for the performance of system to be increased. Following that, a demo prototype is proposed. The implementation strategy was created using the data gathered. Its objective was to fill up the holes in the current infrastructure and get rid of the problems with verification. It is suggested that in a

blockchain design / application made in the future include sections that can be simplified in order to enhance performance of the system.

Research Question	Source of Data	Analysis of Data	Product
<p>What does record security management look like in Zambia?</p> <p>What are the challenges in record security management in the Republic of Zambia?</p> <p>How will proposed blockchain-based solution appear?</p> <p>What does a distributed ledger smart contract solution in the blockchain architecture look like?</p>	<p>Documents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Detailed evaluation reports - Standard operational procedures <p>Flowchart/Process Diagram</p> <p>Blockchain Technology Literature</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Thematic Analysis ➤ Flowchart dataflow diagram <p>Blockchain Adoption Framework</p> <p>Analysis in light of present problem statement</p>	<p>Flowchart DFD</p> <p>Proposed Flowchart DFD</p> <p>Prototype/Demo:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solidity Language - Node.js - React.js - MongoDB (Database) - Binance Smart Chain (BSC)

Table 1. Research Design.

3.2 Modelling

3.2.1 Thematic Content Analysis

According [44], to a qualitative study in which the researcher breaks down the main topic into components and looks at these components. When partial or inadequate theories exist for certain populations and samples, or existing theories do not fully represent the complexity of the topic under consideration, we employ qualitative research to construct theories. The purpose is not aggregative in the sense of "combining research," as in a meta-analysis. This

included a study of papers and past studies documenting the present Bank Record System Management procedure, which included:

- Previous complete evaluation reports
- Strategic papers covering vision and purpose statements, as well as Bank Record Management system targets and goals
- Applicable laws and regulations
- Workflow diagrams and standard operating procedures

This inquiry is required as a result of the requirement to investigate a group or community, find variables that cannot be easily assessed, or hear hushed voices [44]. To develop a new blockchain-based solution to solve identified ongoing issues, it was necessary to first examine the old system in order to recommend a better method. The current pain points were compared to the Bank Blockchain Adoption Framework to recommend an improved registration method.

4. Flow Chart Data Flow Diagram (DFD)

4.1 The Dataflow process Model

The procedure is depicted graphically in the Flowchart/process Data flow diagram. The method is divided into three stages: registration, verifying and storing.

Fig. 1. Current Bank system (Record security management)

Accounts management System includes the systematic tracking, storing, recording, analysing, summarizing, and reporting of financial transactions and changes to accounts. When a customer or client wish to have a new account created in commercial bank, they will be assisted by the teller or cashier in the bank in registering their details and

particulars. Various particulars such as date of birth, full name, nationality etc. will be input into a registration form. The form is available in the English language. In case client isn't English proficient, a translation will be done. The information is manually put into a local register & a request of approval is sent. The higher up registration admins will get a notification. Upon so they can view the notification and then verify the registration of the client or alteration made such as transaction history. Each admin has to approve in order to get that verified. Registration admins can be at different bank branches as this is advised as a safety protocol. In the current bank process various services are offered and the goal of convenience is achieved. Services management deals with loans, ZRA (Zambian Revenue Authority) taxations, NAPSA (National Pension Scheme Authority), Mortgages, Account transfer and more. Under the direction of the Minister of Finance, ZRA is tasked with collecting income on behalf of the Government of the Republic of Zambia. Often there is a deduction of funds from client's accounts, such information can be monitored by numerous personalities from both within the bank as well as Zambia Revenue Authority. After Taxation has been successful the updated transactions particulars will be recorded into the client's file within the bank database. Only after all bank admins approve can this be done. NAPSA, it is a firm or service that was established to offer financial security to working-age people when they reach retirement age (55 years – 65 years of age currently). They also give financial security to a registered member's spouse in the case of death or if a registered member becomes invalid. NAPSA also deals with automatic deduction and once deduction of finances has been done, there will be a request sent to an immediate top admin as well as a notification sent to client. Upon approval this will be sent into the bank database as well as the NAPSA storage be it cloud, database etc. Management Information systems deals with industry financial service. First part of it is Industrial relations, its role is to foster communication between workers and management in order to preserve a healthy working relationship. To build trust between managers and staff. To guarantee that trade unions contribute creatively in order to avert industrial confrontations. Another section is Employee Management, they seek and keep records on manpower that is efficient and competent helps handle the financial risks that banks must face on a daily basis keeping records within the same system upon filing their report higher admins have to approve before particulars are stored into database. Reports from retention management are also stored with the same secure procedure. This department that deals mainly with third-party company databases and employee bank information, things such as salary, loan management when it comes to employees are handled here. It also deals with management of employees within the bank or branch. Retention Management focuses on methods that lead to staff retention. It involves initiatives that have a systematic impact on the binding, performance, and level of loyalty of employees. Internet transactions deals with services related to mobile money services. Clients are at will to link their mobile money accounts with their bank accounts and transaction history is stored and reflected within the bank system without requiring an approval upon insertion. Retail & business banking serves retail consumers, and commercial banks serve corporate and business customers, but most financial organizations have both a retail and a commercial component. Information and particulars involved in International banking such as international transactions, deposits, current changes etc are also part of the repository. Cooperate Banking deals with company customers or co-operations on a large scale and whatever is the outcome or whatever is done is also stored into the system database. Personal Banking which deal with individual banking as well as family banking is also a vital section that has to be protected. Business banking a section that deals with transactions and services offered to businesses and particulars from this are also stored into the database protected by a firewall system. Transaction management is handled by tellers or cashiers, it is also the main-head of debt transactions.

4.1.2 Notifications

During this phase, when one administrator has registered a customer's particulars into the system, other admins will receive a notification that there's a new entry into the database.

Involved Actors	Task in Flowchart
Customer	Payment ZRA, NAPSA, Bank Registration, Load management, Mortgages, registration etc
Bank Teller	Processing of transactions.
Admin	Confirmation of Bank registration and alterations
Super Admin	Management of Admins as whole.

Table 2 Notification Actors and Activities

4.1.3 Decentralised Control: Verification

Administrators examine the pending notifications throughout the verification and validation step, and after confirming their authenticity, they can validate them and approve their storage in the database. The entry can only be stored in the blockchain when it has been approved by all admins.

Involved Actors	Task in Chart
Bank Teller/Cashier	Confirmation of registration request of client as well as alterations made to current stored informatory.

Table 3 Verification Actors and Activities

4.1.4 Quality Assurance: Registration and Transaction Storage

Clients must fill in and submit a of registration form at a local commercial bank. After this, the teller will input the details into an online/electronic form upon this there would be a counter check to ensure there are no mistakes. Once confirmed, the information will be entered into the bank initial phase and it will proceed to the next step in form of a registration request. The physical form will be stamped after verification. All registration will be conducted by a teller at the counter. Often banks keep documents and send copies or scan to the main branch for database storage etc. After verification of documents the bank seal or signature will be on the form. Transaction will also be recorded, things such as deposits or withdraws can be done on mobile or face to face in the bank. Upon completing, the change will be sent to the system as request in updating information such as current balance, balance after withdraw/deposit etc, all these would be stored within the blockchain as well. Banking systems are also linked to the government registration, which can verify the particulars of the client as well.

3. As a result, the only viable means of validation are a single teller's processed information, which risks processing anything the teller or cashier passes forward, whether correct or incorrect.
4. Bank being comfortable with old firewall operation, without a proper modern security measure, cybercrime can occur anytime.
- 5.

Fig 2. Main sharing pain-points

The lack of a sufficiently solid secondary digital verification mechanism as well as guaranteed 100% security was identified as a key concern in the registration, change, and storage operations.

5. Proposed System Architecture

5.1 Proposed system

5.1.1 Data flow architecture

The diagrams and figures in this section depict the architecture and interactions of the blockchain network's participants. The proposed solution is designed to handle the institution's notification and reporting issues. When the alterations as well as additions are input into the system. Each Administrator user receives a new notification. As shown below, Administrators also can add details and edit details and these need to be approved by each of the admins. The bank branches: main branch and smaller branches in this case are considered as nodes on a blockchain network. In this case

we are dealing with one bank branch. Each department creates a block and in the end the blocks are put together as a blockchain ledger then distributed to other bank branches as well as other partners such as ZRA, NAPSA etc. A smart contract is executed to store as well as validate the timestamps. Timestamps will be useful in that they can show what time different tasks and actions were executed; this will encourage the process of backtracking in case needed. A protected timestamp of a transaction's particulars such as time and date, addition or alteration made is very vital when it comes to the maintenance the reliability of transaction transactions and particulars thus serving as a Record Security Management attribute. As time goes on, an increasing number of banks are beginning to gradually prepare for a reduction in the amount of paper work that must be processed. Customers will receive quicker as well as positive benefits such as efficiency and assured security among other things and we must not forget the as well as the experience it will provide the bank. The implementation of Blockchain will enhance the process of identity verification and by cutting off many concerns about the application process.

At this point in time, as technology advances and grows, one of the most important benefits of blockchain technology is that it, when combined with verification in transaction modifications as well as procedures, will minimize both fraud attacks and cyber security risks. The whole banking sector may be protected against dishonest tactics such as money laundering if blockchain technology is used.

Fig.3. Proposed Bank Record Security Management system (Multi-database) (Flow Diagram)

Fig.4. Proposed Bank Record Security Management system (Singular database) IBM Cloud

5.1.2 Within each Actor

Client: The client will be do the first verification even after receiving a text confirming the right information has been inserted into the system before it is sent to the next step for verification.

Teller/ Cashier: They will be in charge of the processes such as registration of new clients to the bank account system. They will also be in-charge of bank in-entry transactions as well as other services. After their work is finished a request will be sent to first admins to verify and confirm the details inserted. Once admin has verified this, it will be insert into a blockchain system.

Super Admin: This is the main admin in charge of dealing with the admins panel, Super admin is not able to edit, delete, handle customers data. Super Admin is able to delete an admin as well as add an admin to the system.

5.1.3 Between Actors

This approach tackles two different situations. Due to lack of proper stable network, banks and financial institutions in rural areas might be slow to process information. In many cases information from rural areas isn't always adequately reported or submitted.

Clients are expected to physically visit a local bank branch of their choice and convenience to complete account registration and other transactional activities. They will often be asked to show their NRC (National registration card) before filling out and submitting a registration form. Commercial banks in your area Currently, they are spread throughout the country. In line with recent method, Blockchain's network is used by the Record Security Management in order to exchange bank branch information from the databases. That way there will be a provision of verifying prior to registration, alteration and permission.

Fig.5. Technology view of implementation

5.1.4 User Layer

The system's administrators and other users are involved in the user layer. It is possible for a single person or a team (group). These make certain that the system is operating effectively and making the most of all of its available resources. As a result of the fact that these users of the bank are responsible for a variety of or a single duty inside the system, the system is able to identify them. Tellers and cashiers, members of the IT team, managers, administrators, super administrators, and maybe even more people might be users of the bank record security management system. The purpose of these users is to interact with the system and make certain that its fundamental operations, which may include registration, reflection, updates, deletion, verification, and others, are carried out effectively. It is possible for the users of the system to access it using a browser or even an application that was designed just for them. These will include a user interface in addition to a suggested framework, which will be shown here as a prototype. The user interface is where the user's functions are stored after they have successfully signed in. Every user has their own set of roles that they are responsible for. The user interface will have some kind of interaction with the subsequent layer, which in this instance will be the blockchain.

5.1.5 Blockchain Layer

The blockchain layer is the second layer in the bank RSM, and it is the layer that includes code or functions that bridge the interaction of users with the browser or application that is operating on a blockchain network. It is composed of three different aspects: -

Assets of Blockchain: Codes of application are used to generate smart contracts, which are then used to verify the contracts before they are implemented on a decentralized blockchain platform or network known as a blockchain network. In this particular instance, we will be using Ethereum as our platform. It is possible for users, administrators, and other external monitories to execute transactions, make alterations to the database, and record information that is saved on the Ethereum network. They are able to simply save this information for further use, either now or in the future, or even forward it on to other people. Because transactions are such significant bits of information, the Ethereum network gives them a high priority. The operation of the blockchain for Ethereum essentially looks like this.

Regulation Governance: When we talk about Blockchain, users are required to comply with a variety of standards. For instance, in order for transactions to be carried out and processed, it is necessary to respect consensus patterns. Consensus and intricate algorithm design have been chosen to serve as the foundation of the BCT in order to guarantee that it will not be changed and will maintain its integrity. Proof-of- The Ethereum blockchain makes use of work, which is an algorithm, to carry out the verification of all transactions and to add a new block to the chain. This is done because

this will ensure that the rules and regulation of blockchain are properly observed and that it is functioning without any problems or doubts with the consent from all trusted members who are connected together within the blockchain.

Network: A peer-to-peer network is one in which each node functions as a server, enabling shared data access and peripherals with a zero need for a central server. To put it another way, all of the linked nodes in the Ethereum network are referred to as peers since the Ethereum network uses a peer-to-peer networking model. There is not a node in the network that is functioning as the central unit while the network is carrying out its typical operations. The most sensible course of action in the implementation of this technology is to create a network in which all of the nodes that are linked have the same status, functionality, and legal rights. All of this is predicated on the concept of developing a separate yet collective platform, as opposed to one that is centred on a single unit or primary source of authority.

Transactions and Records Registration of Clients: The process of registering new bank customers in the system. You may do this in either the browser or the app. The contents include of many fields including name, address, and phone number, as well as other specifics. The fundamental modification history of the client is saved, and the cryptographic hash is given to the smart contract. When it is required, the bank is able to change the information about previous customers as well as add new customers.

5.2 Transactions

5.2.1 Transaction and Registration

Add Client: The following types of transactions are supported by the system: The power or authorization to create a new client file or record in the system via a web browser or desktop program. It includes things like full names, middle names, surnames, phone numbers, nationality, state, city, religion, date of birth, zip code, occupation, ID or National Registration number, particulars of trustee such as full name, phone number, and relation, and it also includes the trustee's particulars such as full name, phone number, and relation. The fundamental data is saved along with a cryptographic hash, which in this instance is a Binance transaction hash. The hash includes not only the file that was uploaded but also additional transactional history and information. the file comprises the client records.

Update records: Both the transactional records and the information about the customers may be changed. To elaborate on this further, the hash cannot be altered; only the fundamental information may be modified. In order to guarantee the integrity of the records, the cryptographic hash cannot be modified.

View records: The application or the browser may be used by the user to access and read the Record Storage of clients that have been saved in the database. The admin, the bank manager, and the teller or cashier all make use of the view feature. A portion of the system makes use of the public account address or key of the client to guarantee that the client is only able to examine information on transactions that are relevant to their needs. The purpose of this is to make it possible for the user to authenticate themselves via the system and examine their own information. As a result, the customer may examine the records and information pertaining to their own transactions.

5.2.2 Furthermore

When the client decides to register a new bank account, once bank staff open the form, the process has officially begun.

In order to register, the customer must provide either their National Registration Card (NRC) or their passport, which contains the customer's information and serves as proof of identity. If a local does not already have an NRC, they are required to get one from the office of the public registration if they do not already have one. When a person reaches the age of 16, they are eligible to get an NRC.

The issues that have been brought to light indicate that there is not a hundred percent guarantee that the information pertaining to clients is safe and secure.

In the last ten years, a significant amount of public funds has vanished after being removed from a bank owing to the lack of a reliable digital verification method.

On a blockchain network, one possible use for bank branches, whether they belong to the same bank or to separate banks, is as nodes.

It is planned to roll out at Blockchain's smart contracts that would have the ability to keep and ensure timestamps are verified.

A bank's timestamp is trustworthy furthermore if any changes made to any account, whether the accounts belong to individuals or businesses. Before the event, a notice will be sent out to all of the administrators.

It is suggested to implement a blockchain-based Record Security Management (RSM) system. A reliable timestamp of the bank registration and any account modifications.

6. Discussion & Conclusion

Even though recent research has investigated the usefulness of blockchain technology, nobody is quite sure how it could be implemented to improve the Bank Record Security Management in developing countries like Zambia. In this piece of research, a blockchain-based banking system is proposed as a potential solution to the problems of cybercrime preparation, developing security issues, and loopholes in Zambia's public funding system. This is the penultimate chapter, and it outlines the many advantages and benefits. Analysis of the practicability of the solution, with the goal of precisely assessing its one-of-a-kind properties, which are necessary for the solution's uncomplicated operation and implementation in a real-world setting.

6.1 Discussion

Before the deployment of Blockchain it is important to take into account some important attributes such as, its advantages, process of execution and also its capabilities.

6.1.1 Benefits in Cost

The reduction or elimination of expenses related to human verification and questionable procedures - It has been stated that a human-based verification of documentation is still carried out by many financial institutions, despite the fact that the existing system does not have a transparent verification method. The suggested automated verification method will result in the complete elimination of any and all associated expenses.

Utilization of public resources in a responsible and efficient manner - The public of the people in the republic of Zambia, as well as the Ministry of Finance and any other stakeholders of the bank, will be able to access and know the statistics of public funds and expenditures in real time if the proposed blockchain solution is implemented, as it suggests that this information will be made available to them. It has the potential to contribute to the effective planning and administration of public resources.

Reduced storage costs - The necessity for banks and other financial institutions to keep their own separate records of notification data is eliminated, which results in lower storage costs. On the other hand, they will have access to a centralized database of the Ministry of Finance or other main-body that is planning for this and will be able to update and add information into it over the internet. This would bring about efficiency by breaking down the barriers between the many storage silos maintained by the various stakeholder entities that share these data.

Cost of registration - The system that has been proposed has the potential to do away with the need for traditional registration Forms. As a subsequent step, higher-ranking bank officers might be in a position to give their stamp of approval to a notification record that has been verified. A technique that is more digital or based on the internet. This can result in a reduction or elimination of the use of the paper-based method, which in turn results in a reduction of the associated operational costs and a reduction in the amount of time required to complete a bank registration and other related matters.

6.1.2 Economical Benefits

In this section part, an economic analysis of the new blockchain-based Bank Record Security Management structure's implementation is developed. In addition, since there is a possibility of risk connected with completely switching over to the new model, the outcomes will vary based on the first section that the financial institution selects in order to evaluate the performance of the new infrastructure. The rationale for this is because: In light of the fact that the new model is not yet in its final form, the analysis is conducted qualitatively.

Transparency between people and their respective government agencies - The establishment of a public transactions ledger makes financial organizations more visible, which might lead to the development of new systems and the reduction of fraudulent practices such as false listing or other types of scams. Because of blockchain technology, transparency may also come about as an immutable record of how various parties in the process performed. An increase in openness will also make it possible for regulators and rating agencies to obtain a better grasp of the risks associated with Bank Record Security Management. Gains in compliance and trust in the government agencies may be realized in addition to a reduction in the potential for risk exposure during operation and transactional expenditures.

Cross Sector Process coordination and Streamlining Interagency - The suggested approach has the potential to make it easier for financial institutions to engage in direct communication with one another. All participants will benefit from increased efficiency in their administration if they have access to a single truth source.

Keeping accurate and permanent records- Not only banks and other financial organizations are the only ones who stand to gain from the use of blockchain technology; there are a plethora of other industries that will also reap the benefits of this innovation. There is a high degree of security and hack prevention built into the system, making it impossible to cheat or corrupt in any way. This is one of the most significant benefits offered by the system. It would be able to develop a blockchain-based system in the bank Record Security Management, and it would be worthwhile to work toward achieving this goal. This would allow for the storage of all of the required information on public and individual financial records. The immutability of a ledger is ensured by the append-only method of updating the blocks, which also improves data integrity and auditability. In addition, the fact that the data are shared on the distributed ledger by various nodes strengthens both the system's level of security and its resilience to harmful behaviour like as cyberattacks.

Increasing Political Prospects and Innovation - Identifies a number of opportunities for more creative use of the blockchain architecture as well as the records. For example, in the future, data from more institutions or nodes may be incorporated, and predictive analytics might potentially be used to the information. The information that was gleaned from the interviews sheds light on a number of novel techniques that may be used to innovate the process. It would seem that every participant is aware of the most important trends and changes that are now taking place. Innovation is mostly driven by a focus on the customer and an efficient use of data. The comments provided a clear view of the industry's favourable attitude towards innovation, which is now prevalent in the Financial sector.

Promote Automatization - Improvements to the registration and verification processes lower the time required to validate a bank registration and record storage occurrence. This might boost the number of registrants, allowing for the increase of achievement of goals.

Society

Verification time Decrease - The potential of the proposed system to cut down on the amount of time required for the registration of banks and the verification of transactions is an important advantage. As the amount of time spent verifying information decreases, the registration procedure may become quicker and, as a result, more convenient for residents, the bank, and the system as a whole.

Participation of citizens at a higher level - As a consequence of the web-based service architecture, the proposed system has the potential to increase citizen engagement while also improving citizens' experiences of service provision and service outcomes. This is made possible thanks to the web-based service design. With the existing method, event

notice may be received anywhere and at any time with only an internet connection and a mobile phone. In addition, transactions that are not being recorded may be readily discovered and tracked in order to guarantee full participation.

Accountability - For the benefit of current and future generations of people, the accessibility and verifiability of information in government registries is made possible by the existence of immutable records. Banks will also be allowed to backtrack.

Reduction or elimination of risks caused by corruption - The system that has been presented makes it possible to verify notification record, and it is not under the control of any participant or group of participants. This separate and unchangeable layer improves the system's resistance to record manipulation and contributes to the fight against the fabrication of phony proof of the use of public funds.

Brand Image: The application of BCT will assist the company in growing, which will result in the company obtaining more trust, which will position the Bank or financial institution as a pioneer and raise the likelihood of a larger and more favourable revaluation.

6.2 Requirements and Challenges of the Proposed System

Despite the fact that the suggested system offers a workable solution to the challenges that now exist, its application in practice needs more investigation, as will be discussed below:

Industrial Partnership & Collaboration. A transition from a decentralized and divided approach to a single and comprehensive integration becomes more realizable thanks to the peer-to-peer interactions that Blockchain enables around shared distributed ledgers. However, this also implies that integration with both currently running processes and future systems is an absolute must. The implementation of the suggested solution requires a number of steps, one of which is the creation of the framework for entities to successfully collaborate with one another. Interoperability is necessary for the synchronization of corporate, stakeholder, and government activities among the appropriate organizations (such as the Ministry of Finance and Bank RSM). This indicates that there must be a working environment that makes use of information shared by several parties.

Blockchain Model of Collaboration - Clarifying the precise sort of blockchain ecosystem and the responsibilities of ecosystem members will be a crucial deployment consideration for the solution. As a structure for a consortium, the following essential functions are proposed:

- Data Providers: All Banks & financial Institutions utilizing the web platform
- Data Users: Commercial Bank(s) / Financial Institution in Zambia.
- Data Validators: Ministry of Finance IT/Security team.

Collection Management, Data Protocols and Distribution - Set of services connected to the collections that serve for their administration, the formulation of strategic strategies, or the storage and maintenance of the works in the collections. It is necessary to take into consideration both on-chain and off-chain architectures if one wishes to maximize the value of the information that is obtained as a result of implementing the solution. Even if the data will be entirely decentralized and shared among all nodes in order to allow resistance to attack, it is possible that the whole data will be stored in the official database of the bank, while only the necessary data and matching hashes will be stored on the blockchain. Important concerns about data standards, such as data privacy, are examples of such concerns.

Information Technology Infrastructure and Applications - Considerations for technologies such as cloud computing or networking topologies, satellite-based or server-based time servers, and the provision of basic computer equipment for the required offices will be among the core needs for implementation. The solution that has been proposed is a system based on the web that makes use of timestamp and cryptographic technologies.

6.3 Feasibility

When it comes to putting in place the new infrastructure, banks, other financial institutions, and the government all have certain considerations that need to be taken into account, which are outlined in this part of the new blockchain-based model. It is true, taking into consideration how the model has been created and constructed, that a significant portion of the vulnerabilities and dangers posed by the existing cryptographic environment have been eliminated. On the one hand, the environmental effect is kept to a minimum because of the kind of network that was selected, and on the other hand, the model is still a novel implementation of eco sustainable software.

Competency - As a result of its previous work, it is familiar with the broad criteria that must be met before the implementation of such a solution. Users will need very little to no expertise if the front-end is designed to be user-friendly. However, in order to design and administer the Blockchain architecture and interface, either highly qualified blockchain specialists or top third-party development businesses would be required.

Technical Feasibility - This research proposes a web-based interface that will enable users to access the system through mobile phones, tablets, and personal computers.

Scalability - As development accelerates, it is anticipated that the government will also expand. Technology should evolve and expand. reflecting the definition of scalability as the capacity of a system to grow in response to varying application processing demands

Government Regulations As of right now, there are already government agencies working on developing a legally binding rule for all cryptographic assets. Laws and international standards or protocols for Bank Record security management, a critical statistic that is fully supported, will be adhered to, and deployed nodes will make sure to keep track of them. Issues connected to data privacy and associated rules that assure the utilization of data by organizations such as banks, other financial institutions, and the government are of secondary importance to the successful deployment of a solution.

7. Conclusion

The Blockchain Technology is a fascinating technology that has seen exponential growth over the last few years. This growth has led to the development of a variety of applications that have the potential to change numerous facets of the FINTECH industry. In the specific instance of the matter that is discussed in the thesis, financial institutions like banks and many other types of financial institutions have been among the most potentially affected. This study introduced and also demonstrated a blockchain-based design solution for resolving issues such as loss of public fund, prevention of cybercrime, clients' information as well as secure transactional records in the Commercial Bank in Zambia. The study is contributing with an improved knowledge about blockchain technology and its potential and challenge within the real-time banking. Thematic study of previously published material, the direction provided by the Bank Blockchain adoption Framework, and the creation of a process model were all necessary steps in achieving this goal. The model for the semi-through process was developed. After that, the purpose of the research was to determine the underlying problems that crop up throughout the process of transactional verification. The suggestions from the research done by Bank RSM were used to guide a massive portion of the design process. In conclusion, a solution based on blockchain technology is suggested in order to overcome the problems that were previously addressed. In the third level, you will provide a suggestion for an architectural design and put together a prototype to demonstrate a portion of the recommended solution.

7.1 Study Limitation

The breadth of this study necessarily encompasses some of its shortcomings. The purpose of this research is to investigate Zambia's Bank Record Security Management and to provide a fresh approach for improving it. The suggested blockchain technique does solve the process's present pain points and issues; nonetheless, the scope of this research is limited. To provide just one example, the data sources are limited to actual research that has been published.

An empirical investigation may be carried out in order to verify the correctness of the procedures that were found. In addition, this study does not contain any research that was conducted on technical or legal topics. Since the author does not have adequate awareness of these subjects, we will not be discussing them further. The bulk of current research on blockchain technology is focused on the construction of various frameworks, which is typical for research into new technologies in general.

7.2 Suggestions for Future Research

The findings of this study might be replicated by other researchers, who would then investigate whether or not the framework is applicable in cross-cultural contexts. As this is one of the very few pieces of published research on bank record security that makes use of a blockchain, further research is needed before an application can be developed to test the idea. In addition, research might be carried out on the legal and technological issues of the implementations.

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